

Infrared Spectra of some Nitrones, Azoxybenzenes, O-Methyloximes and Sydnones

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The infrared spectra of a number of nitrones, azoxybenzenes, O-methyloximes and sydnones have been determined. The N→O and N–O stretching frequencies are given. The N→O frequencies of ketonitrones are higher than those of aldonitrones. In both aldo- and keto-nitrones the N→O vibration occurs at a higher frequency in the N-alkyl compound than in the corresponding N-aryl compound. The N→O frequencies are affected by the electronic interaction between the substituents and azomethine linkage across the benzene ring.

THE absorption spectra of a number of nitrones and related compounds were studied as a part of our investigation dealing with the steric and electronic effects in them^{1,2}. In this paper we report the infrared spectra of a number of compounds having nitrogen–oxygen linkage. Assignments for the N→O and N–O stretching frequencies are made by comparing their spectra with those of the structurally related compounds but without the particular vibration which is considered for the assignment.

Experimental

The N-phenylnitrones, azomethines and azoxybenzenes were prepared as described earlier^{1,2}, and *syn*- and *anti*-oximes, N-methylnitrones and O-methyloximes were prepared as described in the literature³⁻⁶.

N-Methyl- α,α -diphenylnitron, m.p. 91–2° (lit.³ 102–03°) (Found: C, 79.4; H, 6.5. C₁₄H₁₃NO calcd. for: C, 79.6; H, 6.2%) ; 4,4'-Dimethoxybenzophenone-O-methyloxime, m.p. 86–7° (Found: C, 71.0; H, 6.4. C₁₆H₁₇NO₃ calcd. for: C, 70.8; H, 6.3%) ; 4,4'-Dimethylbenzophenone-O-methyloxime, m.p. 97–8° (Found: C, 80.4; H, 7.3. C₁₆H₁₇NO calcd. for: C, 80.3; H, 7.2%) ; *syn*-Oxime of p-chlorobenzaldehyde, m.p. 110–11° (lit.⁵ 106–07°) ; *syn*-O-Methyloxime of p-chlorobenzaldehyde, b.p. 99–100°/15 mm; n_D²⁰ 1.5620 (lit.⁵ m.p. 28°) (Found: C, 56.5; H, 4.6. C₉H₈ClNO calcd. for: C, 56.7; H, 4.8%) ; N-(p-Methylbenzylidene)aniline, m.p. 46–7° (lit.⁷ 46.5–48°).

Sydnones: The compounds were prepared by the methods described in the literature⁸⁻¹⁰.

The ir spectra (KBr) were determined on a Beckmann IR double beam spectrophotometer.

Results and Discussion

N→O stretching frequency: The information available in the literature on the ir spectra of nitrones is very scanty¹¹. A brief account of the studies made on the N→O frequency of N-oxides of pyridines and pyrimidines, and tertiary amine oxides is given by Bellamy¹². This absorption is reported to occur in 1310–1200 cm⁻¹ region.

In both aldo- and keto-nitrones, the N→O frequency of an N-alkyl compound is at a higher range than the corresponding N-aryl compound (Table 1, sl. nos. 6 and 14, 10 and 15, 16 and 17). A similar

TABLE 1—THE N→O STRETCHING FREQUENCIES OF NITRONES

Sl. no.	Nitron	$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹
1.	N, α -Diphenyl	1069} ^a 1083} 1072} ^a 1091} 1067} ^a 1081}
2.	N-(p-Chlorophenyl)- α -phenyl	1071
3.	α -Phenyl-N-p-tolyl	1086
4.	N-Phenyl- α -p-tolyl	1076} ^a 1093}
5.	α -(p-Chlorophenyl)-N-p-tolyl	1074
6.	α -(p-Chlorophenyl)-N-phenyl	1089
7.	α -(p-Bromophenyl)-N-phenyl	1111
8.	α -(p-Methoxyphenyl)-N-phenyl	1069
9.	α -(p-Nitrophenyl)-N-phenyl	1111
10.	α -(m-Nitrophenyl)-N-phenyl	1069
11.	α -(p-Hydroxyphenyl)-N-phenyl	1061
12.	α -(o-Hydroxyphenyl)-N-phenyl	1089
13.	N-Phenyl- α -styryl	1054
14.	α -(p-Chlorophenyl)-N-methyl	1071} ^a 1183}
15.	N-Methyl- α -(m-nitrophenyl)	1180
16.	α,α -Diphenyl-N-methyl	1252
17.	N, α,α -Triphenyl	1239
18.	α -(p-Chlorophenyl)-N, α -diphenyl	1240
19.	α -(p-Bromophenyl)-N, α -diphenyl	1240

^aSplit band.

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observation was made in the ir spectra of *N*-methyl- α -phenylnitronone and *N*, α -diphenylnitronone for which the N $\rightarrow$ O frequency is reported¹¹ to be 1 172 and 1 088 cm⁻¹, respectively. In ketonitrones, the N $\rightarrow$ O frequency shifted to a higher range (Table 1, sl. nos. 6 and 18, 7 and 19). This is presumably due to neither of the benzene rings conjugating with the C=N bond. Steric hindrance prevents the rings from being coplanar with the C=N bond. That a steric factor is operative in ketonitrones is also evident from the uv spectra of aldo- and ketonitrones given in Table 2; $\epsilon_{\max}$ of the long wavelength band is very much reduced for ketonitrones, indicating the steric inhibition of resonance in them.

TABLE 2—SELECTIVE UV ABSORPTIONS OF NITRONES IN ETHANOL (95%)

Nitronone	$\lambda_{\max}$ nm	$\epsilon_{\max}$
<i>N</i> -Methyl- α -phenyl	292	21 150
	223	8 700
<i>N</i> -Methyl- α , α -diphenyl	296	10 350
	235	12 400
<i>N</i> , α -Diphenyl	314	20 600
	230	10 500
<i>N</i> , α , α -Triphenyl	311	10 700
	234	14 700
α -(<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl)- <i>N</i> , α -diphenyl	314	12 000
	250	15 900

In aldonitrones the N $\rightarrow$ O stretching bands are very strong and in many cases doublets are observed. The N $\rightarrow$ O band is sensitive to the electronic effects of the substituents on the phenyl rings. In α -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-*N*-phenylnitronone then N $\rightarrow$ O frequency is 1 069 cm⁻¹, whereas the same in α -(*p*-nitrophenyl)-*N*-phenylnitronone occurs at 1 111 cm⁻¹. Similar electronic effects were also observed from the study of their dipole moments².

In azoxybenzenes the N $\rightarrow$ O stretching frequency occurs in the range 1 285–1 260 cm⁻¹ (Table 3). Jander and Hazeldine¹² reported a similar frequency range (1 310–1 250 cm⁻¹) for N $\rightarrow$ O absorption in azoxymethanes.

 TABLE 3—THE N $\rightarrow$ O STRETCHING FREQUENCIES OF *trans*-AZOXYBENZENES

Azoxybenzene	$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹
4,4'-Difluoro	1 276
4,4'-Dichloro	1 282
4,4'-Dibromo	1 284
3,3'-Dichloro	1 270
4,4'-Dimethyl	1 262
4,4'-Diethoxy	1 266

N $\rightarrow$ O Stretching frequency: Previous investigators reported the N $\rightarrow$ O stretching vibration at different frequencies. This is mainly because of the small number of compounds they examined. The correct assignment was also made difficult due to

the presence of overlapping absorption bands. In the present study, the N–O frequency has been fixed by comparing the ir spectra of structurally similar compounds having no N–O bond.

There is evidence in literature for the assignment of the N–O stretching mode to the 900 cm⁻¹ region^{14,16} and 850–800 cm⁻¹ region^{17,18}. From a study of the ir spectra of aldoximes and their *N*-methyl and *O*-methyl derivatives, Palm and Werbin¹⁹ tentatively assigned the strong bands occurring at 940 and 850 cm⁻¹ to the N–O stretching vibration and C–H bending mode, respectively. Their assignment to the N–O bond does not seem to be correct because the band at 940 cm⁻¹ is shown by the oximes as well as by their *N*- and *O*-methyl derivatives. We were, therefore, prompted to study the ir spectra of a number of *O*-methyloximes and sydnones where the N–O bond is purely a covalent one. Since the force constant of a single bond is less than that of a coordinate covalent bond, one can expect the N–O stretching frequency to be less than 1 100 cm⁻¹. The frequencies of the important bands observed in the range 1 100–800 cm⁻¹ for the *O*-methyloximes are given in Table 4 along with those of azomethines and nitrones for a comparative study.

 TABLE 4—IMPORTANT IR BANDS (IN THE REGION 1 100–800 cm⁻¹) OF *O*-METHYL ETHERS OF OXIMES, NITRONES AND AZOMETHINES

Sl. no.	Compd.	$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹
1.	(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ C=N.OCH ₃	864s 989 1 055
2.	$\begin{matrix} \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C}=\text{N.OCH}_3 \\ \diagup \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \end{matrix}$	826 880s 982 1 059
3.	(<i>p</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄) ₂ C=N.OCH ₃	829 880s 980 1 059
4.	(<i>p</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄) ₂ C=N.OCH ₃	841 884s 985 1 056
5.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .OH=N.OCH ₃	833 849s 923 1 051
6.	<i>m</i> -O ₂ N.C ₆ H ₄ .OH=N.OCH ₃	818 846s 940 1 050
7.	$\begin{matrix} \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C}=\text{N.OCH}_3 \\ \diagup \\ \text{O} \end{matrix}$	880 865w 952
8.	$\begin{matrix} \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C}=\text{N.OCH}_3 \\ \diagup \\ \text{O} \end{matrix}$	827 862w 954
9.	(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ C=N.C ₆ H ₅	963
10.	$\begin{matrix} \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C}=\text{N.C}_6\text{H}_5 \\ \diagup \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \end{matrix}$	833 959
11.	(C ₆ H ₅) ₂ C=N.OH ₂	978
12.	$\begin{matrix} \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C}=\text{N.C}_6\text{H}_5 \\ \diagup \\ \text{O} \end{matrix}$	961
13.	$\begin{matrix} \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C}=\text{N.C}_6\text{H}_5 \\ \diagup \\ \text{C}_6\text{H}_5 \end{matrix}$	845 956
14.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .OH=N.C ₆ H ₅	833 882w 975
15.	<i>p</i> -OH.C ₆ H ₄ .OH=N.C ₆ H ₅	818 880w 985
16.	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄ .OH=N.C ₆ H ₅	844 895w 919

s=strong, w=weak.

The *O*-methyloximes of ketones (Table 4, sl. nos. 1–4) show three or four bands in the above range.

The strong band around 1055 cm^{-1} found in the spectra of all the *O*-methyloximes of both ketones and aldehydes, is due to C—O stretching vibration. Substitution in the phenyl rings has little effect on this band. Another very strong band, observed at $845\text{--}810\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is due to two adjacent H atoms in the benzene ring²⁰. It is shown by all the compounds having 1,4-substituted-phenyl group or groups. It is significant that this band is not observed for the compounds with sl. nos. 1, 9, 11 and 12 (Table 4) which have unsubstituted-phenyl groups, i.e. with five adjacent ring H atoms. These compounds, however, have very strong absorption in the $770\text{--}730$ and $710\text{--}690\text{ cm}^{-1}$ regions as expected²⁰. Of the two remaining strong bands at $985\text{--}915$ and $885\text{--}880\text{ cm}^{-1}$, the former which are observed in the case of all compounds (Table 4), are due to out-of-plane deformation vibrations of the hydrogen atoms of the benzene ring as strong bands are known to appear in the region $1000\text{--}650\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of aromatic compounds²¹. So the strong bands appearing in the $885\text{--}880\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region for *O*-methyloximes of ketones are due to N—O stretching. A similar band at $895\text{--}860\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is present in the spectra of aldnitrones and Schiff bases of aldehydes but having much less intensity. This may be assigned to C—H out-of-plane bending frequency due to the α -hydrogen present on the azomethine linkage. This view gains support from the observation that this band disappears when the α -hydrogen is replaced by a phenyl group (Table 4, sl. nos. 9—13).

The N—O bond vibration in the *O*-methyloximes of aldehydes (sl. nos. 5 and 6) occurs at a lower frequency (849 and 846 cm^{-1}) than that (around 880 cm^{-1}) in *O*-methyloximes of ketones (sl. nos. 1—4). This assignment seems to be correct because these bands are absent in the corresponding nitrones which show absorption characteristic of the N—O bond (Table 1). Furthermore, the N—O stretching frequency in $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{O}$ being less than that in $\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{O}$ (with α -substitution) seems to be similar to the C—O stretching frequency in $-\text{CH}=\text{C}-\text{O}$ of anisoles being less than that in the corresponding *ortho*-substituted-anisoles²². It may also be noted that the N—O stretching vibration occurs at $861\text{--}848\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for sydnones (Table 5).

Sydnones: The important band frequencies observed in the spectra of sydnones are given in Table 5. The first band observed at 1760 cm^{-1} is assigned to C=O stretching frequency^{23,24}. The reduction of carbonyl frequency to 1754 cm^{-1} in *N-p*-methoxyphenylsydnone when compared to 1773 cm^{-1} of *N*-phenylsydnone is presumably due to the conjugative interaction of the heterocyclic nucleus containing the carbonyl group with the

TABLE 5—INFRARED ABSORPTION OF SYDNONES

R	$\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ cm^{-1}	$\nu_{\text{C}-\text{O}}$ cm^{-1}	$\nu_{\text{N}-\text{O}}$ cm^{-1}
H	1 773	1 090	856
CH ₃	1 773	1 085	859
Cl	1 779	1 099	861
OCH ₃	1 754	1 098	848

methoxyl of the phenyl ring. The band around 1090 cm^{-1} is due to C—O stretching vibration as in *O*-methyloximes. The remaining strong band occurring at $861\text{--}848\text{ cm}^{-1}$ can only be due to the N—O stretching frequency and this region is not very far away from the one assigned to the N—O vibration in *O*-methyloximes of aldehydes.

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